

**A LEARNING ORGANIZATION AND SMES ABILITY TO APPLY
THIS CONCEPT GIVEN THEIR INHERITED CONSTRAINTS AND
LIMITATIONS**

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Abstract: The number of small and medium businesses is currently growing quickly on a global scale, and the further transformation of those SMEs can occasionally be much more challenging than anticipated since the world is undergoing major changes. Today, almost everything is changing quickly, including the market conditions, customers and trends. Hence, all types of businesses are being forced by these changes to make significant efforts in order to remain competitive in the market. As a result, most large organizations are also facing difficulties and are quickly taking steps and making efforts to become learning organizations in order to secure their current and future growth.

Key words: SME, Learning organization, growth, small business, transformation into a learning organization

A learning organization is a modern innovation that has been extensively applied in business settings during the past couple of decades. The term "learning organization" refers to an organization's capacity to continually develop its skills through the implementation of an internal learning process that guarantees that everyone inside the organization remains cohesive and has access to fresh sources of information. Businesses had to contend with numerous unexpected factors as the world moved toward digitalization, in addition to the harsh rivalry brought on by globalization and the internet they had to deal with rising concern on environmental issues as well as changing customer expectations. As a result, they began to think about how to remain

strong and competitive in such an unstable environment and this is where the learning organization concept was put to use. Many people realized that by using this concept to their companies, they could remain competitive for long and quickly adjust to the current market conditions, which call for being agile and behaving agile.

Learning organizations rather than investing all of their human, time, and financial resources on present tactics allocate some of their resources to thinking about potential future profitable areas for their company’s growth. They make an investment in long-term learning processes and spend time thinking about future-related themes and issues in order to be prepared for any unforeseen or anticipated changes and handle them successfully.

The steps for becoming a learning organization:

- Actively evaluate how your organization operates and create new working methods. Organizations that employ critical thinking techniques are able to step back and consider how precisely their organization operates as well as ways to increase its effectiveness and efficiency.

- Invest in employee training, development, and advancement – Organizations cannot foster a culture of learning without giving employees significant support in developing new abilities and expanding their understanding of management, business, and marketing strategies.

- Introduce initiatives that encourage a culture of ongoing education and lifelong learning – Most employers desire to create a staff that is always developing and improving, but not all do so. Companies that change from a typical company culture to a learning organization frequently have a plan for how they're going to encourage employees to constantly push themselves forward and make learning an essential component of the job.

According to Peter Stenge, who wrote a book *The Fifth Discipline* a learning organization is "a place where people continually expand their capacity to create the results they desire, where new and creative thinking is nurtured, where collective

thinking is empowered, and where people are continually learning how to learn together,".

In light of this explanation, we can state that a learning organization is the one in which fresh ideas are encouraged and new talent is given the chance to flourish. This definition is extremely similar to the idea of corporate intrapreneurship, which also refers to the development of fresh ideas and new knowledge within the organization. Companies with a long-term vision understand that investing in the professional development of their staff is a crucial step in securing their own future. Accordingly, we see a huge number of large firms putting a lot of work into becoming a learning company through various programs and projects like corporate intrapreneurship. But what about small and medium enterprises, are they able to transform themselves into learning organizations. Given that small enterprises lack the resources that large organizations possess, the question of whether they can transform themselves into learning organizations arises. Although small businesses are renowned for their adaptability and creativity in their operations, will this be sufficient to make up for the other resources they lack and enable them to become learning organizations?

Businesses, big or small, that want to remain competitive in today's fast-paced, constantly changing world must have the ability to both respond to the changes and constantly bring changes to the market area. Managers that are unable or unwilling to successfully implement changes to match market trends and consumer needs will lose their clients and market position.

When business fails, evidence usually existed in advance that the firm was in trouble (Kiechel & Sampson, 1993). Majority of business leaders often are unable to recognize or stay ignorant to the foreseeable threats to the organization and respectively, they face huge irresistible problems that then makes their business to fail or endure huge losses. Constant threats to corporations as a whole include the turnover in economics, redistribution of production resources to new companies, and development of new cultures. The symptom of high corporation mortality rates may represent the deeper

problems that afflict all companies. Some will not survive, and more importantly, some will never live up to their potential. Senge, (1990) associated these results with corporate learning disability. Indeed, regardless of their size, many businesses fail to apply fundamental concepts of a learning organization upon the interfering formal bureaucracy and other internal cultural elements that present in the workplace.

Most organizations are still struggling to become learning organizations, while many others still don't grasp the importance of the process or how it can actually work (Marquardt, 2002). From a small business perspective, it is even more difficult to pursue this goal on a tight budget. (Chinh T. Bui, 2009) Due to their inherent characteristics, small and medium-sized organizations are more likely to operate in a chaotic manner where they may deal with uncertainty and ambiguity in the assignment of roles and responsibilities. In addition to the above issues, they have numerous other challenges such as limited access to additional financial resources to compete with other large enterprises in their chosen sector. They frequently find it challenging to take their focus off of daily operations and think about future plans, especially the process of knowledge growth, as a result of all of these factors they are forced to exist in a stressful and erratic atmosphere to survive.

Organizational learning may be a crucial and successful small business strategy to support sustainable development, but Wyer, Mason and Theodorakopoulos (2000) argued that the leaders of learning organizations, as currently envisioned in the mainstream literature, fail to recognize and address the issues and limitations specific to sustainable small business. The ability to have a better knowledge of the relationships between the five learning organization disciplines and the insights into the performance of the learning organization in an organization that has effectively adopted this idea is one of the concerns for a small business (Chinh T. Bui, 2009).

Studies and prior research support the idea that changing a firm into a learning organization, especially a small one, is more difficult in comparison with the transformation of huge corporations. Since there hasn't been enough study on how SMEs expand and change into learning organizations, it is important to encourage

SMEs to learn and rely on existing examples of successful SMEs that have done so and apply those strategies to their own situations. To help small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) become as competitive as giant corporations, more research is needed on how to help them transform into learning organizations.

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